

The Study of Personality of Secondary School Teachers of Garhwal Region

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ABSTRACT

Teaching is a practical endeavor that always involves the teacher's performance or presentation, and it is fundamentally an expression of personality. Teaching is a practice rather than a job since knowledge never deteriorates and teaching never gets old. Teachers have a crucial role in teaching and learning because they must be excellent role models for their students. Effective teachers employ a range of strategies throughout the day, taking into account the learning goals, the number of students participating, the characteristics of the students, the resources available, and so forth. The main objective of the research paper is to find out the significant difference of Personality of teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools of Garhwal Region of Uttarakhand state. A sample size of 197 teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools of Garhwal Region of Uttarakhand state were selected and taken up for the study. Dimensional Personality Inventory developed by Mahesh Bhargava was used for the study. It has been found that, there is no significant difference of Personality of teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools of Garhwal Region of Uttarakhand state. In light of the fact that the classroom climate is heavily influenced by the personality of the teacher, they should be able to

build and maintain a conducive atmosphere that helps the students for effective learning.

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Introduction

The main role model in the learning process is the instructor. Teachers are the one who think that effective teaching strategies should be used. The traits of teachers account for a great deal of variation in the quality of instruction; they are essential to the teaching and learning process, play a significant part in shaping students' personalities, and serve as learning managers in a vast educational system that enlightens students. As a result, they are able to act in ways that are dictated by their conscience, their sincere appearance devoid of deception, their concern for the preservation of social ethics, their personal qualities of honesty, democratization, tolerance, and peace of life, and their ability to respond to all issues that the country and society face. To put it briefly, educators have a significant impact on the development of individuals who are morally upright, courteous, skilled in debating, and graceful in their day-to-day interactions. Thus, in order to raise student accomplishment, teachers' quality needs to be increased. There are intricate demands placed on teachers' quantity and quality.

Personality cannot be interpreted as a person's external presence or actions. It is impossible to ignore the personality's inner dimension. As a result, personality encompasses all of an individual's actions, both within and outside the body. This includes all of the things that people do to each other and to other people. It demands a person's bodily, financial, social, mental, and spiritual well-being. Personality, then, is who you are. A person is all about himself. It includes all behavioral patterns including social behaviors that impact psychomotor activity, which includes both awareness and sub consciousness that are found in conscience. Each person has a unique and unique temperament. We are all distinct individuals. Even though they may not have a personality, infants develop one through constant communication with their environment. Hence, the researcher is interested and makes sincere effort to verify and test the personality of teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools of Garhwal Region of Uttarakhand state.

Significance of the study

A teacher plays an important role in the student's personality development. When the teacher asks

questions, shows interest, understands their thoughts, and appreciates, it increases their motivation. Giving feedback for their work, complimenting, and wanting to listen helps them. Non-verbal actions and gestures like smiling, improve the students learning development. When the teacher supports the student, it makes a lot of difference in his personality. Students whose teachers displayed positive attitudes will have a positive attitude. For this reason, the researcher is interested in and makes a sincere effort to verify and test the personality of teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools, along with personality of male and female teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools of Garhwal Region of Uttarakhand state.

Statement of the problem

The problem for the present study is stated as follows:

“The Study of Personality of Secondary School Teachers of Garhwal Region”

Operational definition of the term Personality

A teacher's personality is made up of a variety of qualities, such as their ability to communicate, empathy, patience, and flexibility. Students can be motivated to succeed and an interesting learning environment can be created by a competent teacher's personality. Personality is a distinctive style of feeling, thinking, and doing. Moods, attitudes, and opinions are all part of personality, which is best shown in social interactions. It encompasses both innate and learned behavioral traits. In the present study Personality variables of teacher refers to score obtained on Dimensional Personality Inventory (DPI) developed by Mahesh Bhargava.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the significant difference of personality of teacher of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools.
2. To study the significant difference of personality of male and female teacher of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools.

Hypothesis of the study

1. There is no significant difference of personality of teacher of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools.
2. There is no significant difference of personality of male and female teacher of Sugam

Government secondary schools.

3. There is no significant difference of personality of male and female teacher of Durgam Government Secondary Schools.

Research Methodology

The sampling method which was adopted in the study was multistage random sampling method. At first from Garhwal region at first districts were selected, then blocks and then schools. Out of six districts of Garhwal Region namely, Chamoli, Dehradun, Haridwar, Pauri, Rudraprayag, Tehri and Uttarkashi three districts namely, Dehradun, Haridwar and Pauri. Total number of selected secondary schools in Garhwal Region were 27, out of which 15 were Sugam secondary schools and similarly 12 were Durgam secondary schools. There were total 197 secondary teachers from the selected secondary school, out of which 116 were teachers of Sugam secondary schools and 81 were from Durgam secondary schools. Gender wise there were 135 male teachers and 62 female teachers from Sugam and Durgam secondary schools. Further in Sugam secondary schools there were 79 male and 37 female teachers and in Durgam secondary school there were 56 male and 25 female teachers.

Tools used

The researcher has used the Dimensional Personality Inventory of Mahesh Bhargava for the present study.

Analysis

1. Personality of teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools.

Table No. 1

Variable	Teachers	Mean	S.D	df	't' value
Personality	Sugam	56.83	15.03	195	1.837
	Durgam	50.19	13.24		

Interpretation

Personality of teachers of Sugam government secondary schools is 56.83, and of Durgam government secondary school is 50.19. The obtained value of “t” =1.837 is less than the table value with df 195 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.96 and at 0.01 level i.e. 2.59. Thus the Ho-1 is accepted.

Justification

It is observed that the instructors at both locations are dynamic, vivacious, enthusiastic, upbeat, straightforward in their approach to life, and flexible. Teachers at both locations are subject to the same administrative oversight and have undergone the same selection process for this position.

2. Personality of male and female teacher of Sugam Government Secondary Schools.

Table No. 2

Variable	Sugam	Mean	S.D	df	‘t’ value
		Personality	Male		
	Female	53.86	14.59		

Interpretation

The mean of personality of male teachers is 57.05, and of female teachers is 53.86 of Sugam government secondary school. The obtained value of “t” = 1.338 is smaller than the table value with df 114 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98 and at 0.01 level i.e. 2.59. Thus the Ho-2 is accepted.

Justification

The mean of Personality of female teachers is Lower than the male teachers of Sugam Secondary school. Results show that no significant difference has found between male and female teachers of Sugam secondary school as difference in gender is not the only cause of difference in Personality.

3. Personality of male and female teacher of Durgam Government Secondary Schools.

Table No. 3

Variable	Durgam				

		Mean	S.D	df	't' value
Personality	Male	46.87	10.95	79	3.114**
	Female	54.11	15.07		

The mean of personality of male teachers of is 46.87, and of female teachers of Durgam government secondary school is 54.11. The obtained value of "t" =3.114 is greater than the table value with df 79 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.96 and at 0.01 level i.e. 2.59. Thus the Ho-3 is rejected.

Justification

Male and female teachers of Durgam Secondary schools were significantly different in Personality. And it is evident from the data that the mean of Personality of male teachers of Durgam Secondary school is Lower than the female teachers of Durgam Secondary school.

Conclusion

The finding of the study shows that there is no significant difference of personality of teachers of Sugam and Durgam Government Secondary Schools of Garhwal region of Uttarakhand State. It means locality, types of school do not influence the personality. The enthusiasm among teachers in both types of the schools located in sugam and durgam area would be high. Similarly, the Male and Female Teachers of Sugam Secondary School do not differ significantly in their Personality. However, the Male and Female Teachers of Durgam Secondary School differ significantly in their Personality. It means somehow gender may or may not influence the personality. The survival, strength, effectiveness, and success of the institution are significantly influenced by the personality of the teacher. Even with great material resources, a school's entire curriculum is likely to be unproductive and wasteful if the teachers are not effective. If the behavior of the teaching staff is not satisfactory and effective, the syllabus, textbooks, and other teaching aids lose their value and usefulness. Therefore, a teacher's personality is a major factor in the formation of an organization. It is a prerequisite for success in every educational setting.

Recommendation

- The present investigation concentrated on Personality and its dimensions on secondary school teachers. A further study of this kind may be continued for teachers, who are working in pre-primary, primary, upper primary schools and assistant professor working in professional and non- professional colleges at different levels of education.

- Each dimension of Personality may be taken up separately for further investigation on different samples of people.
- A comparative study may be done among Personality of pre-primary, primary, upper primary school teachers as well as other teaching community.
- Other cognitive correlated and contra indicative factors of Personality may also be studied.
- Programs adopted for the development of Personality in schools, colleges and other educational institutions may be carried out.

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